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STRICTLY PROTECTED SPECIES OF HOVERFLIES (Diptera: Syrphidae) IN SERBIA IN THE FACE OF CLIMATE CHANGE

ABSTRACT: Climate change is happening. Due to a spectrum of possible consequences, numerous studies examine the effects of global warming on species distribution. This study examines the effects of changing climate on distribution of selected strictly protected species of hoverflies in Serbia, by using species distribution modelling. Ten species were included in the analysis. Three species were predicted to lose a part of their range across time, while for seven species the range expansion was predicted. Both in the present time and in the future, mountainous regions have the highest species richness, such as Golija, Kopaonik, and Prokletije in the western Serbia, and mountains Stara Planina, Besna Kobila, Suva Planina, and Dukat in the southeastern part of the country. However, beside climate change, there are several other factors that might influence the distribution of strictly protected hoverflies in Serbia, such as intensive land use and degradation of habitats. Additionally, global warming also affects flowering plants that syrphids are dependent on, which could present another obstacle to their future range expansions. These results can contribute to planning future steps for the conservation of strictly protected hoverfly species.

KEYWORDS: global warming, insects, strictly protected species, species distribution modelling

INTRODUCTION

Over the past 100 years, the global average temperature has increased by approximately 0.6 °C (Root et al., 2003; Bale et al., 2010). This is an undisputable evidence that climate change is happening. Numerous researches deal with the effects of changing climate on biodiversity (Ramsfield, 2016; Westphal et al., 2016; Miličić et al., 2018; Radenković et al., 2018). Studies showed that

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regional climate changes can influence species in different ways: they can move their area of occupancy in order to find suitable environment, alter their phenology in the attempt to adapt to new conditions, or become extinct (Thuiller et al., 2008; Lurgi et al., 2012). Narrow geographic range, limited dispersal capacity, low reproductive output and a high degree of habitat specialization are traits that make species particularly prone to environmental changes (Isaac et al., 2009). These characteristics are almost certainly present in species with restricted distribution, which makes them particularly sensitive to ecosystem changes.

Hoverflies represent an important pollinator group (Jauker et al., 2012; Inouye et al., 2015) with more than 6,000 described species. Beside pollination, this Dipteran family can be significant as indicator of environmental changes (Meyer et al., 2009; Sommaggio and Burgio, 2014). Additionally, hoverflies have an important role in decomposition of materials such as dead wood, compost, dung, rotting aquatic vegetation, and so on, but can also be used for decomposition of organic material from agricultural and industrial processes.

One of the steps in preserving species is their legal protection. Under the national legislation of Serbia 44 species of hoverflies are listed as protected, while 33 species are categorised as being strictly protected. The aim of this study was to estimate the potential effects of climate change on the distribution of strictly protected hoverfly species in Serbia by using species distribution modelling. This method is successfully applied in numerous studies dealing with the effects of climate change on species distributions (Guo et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2018).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Distribution data for all species listed as protected in Serbia were extracted from the database of the Department of Biology and Ecology of the University of Novi Sad. The species that had more than five different occurrence points were kept and used for further analyses, while others were dropped out. For building species distribution models, 19 bioclimatic variables were used describing current climate obtained from the WorldClim dataset (Hijmans et al., 2005) in 30 arc sec resolution. Regarding the future bioclimatic variables, climate projections were used at the same resolution from the global climate models used in the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC 2014).

To reduce collinearity, modelling was conducted in two stages. In the first stage, all bioclimatic variables were used for model building, while in the second step, modelling was repeated using only stronger predictor variables (with more than 10% contribution in the initial run). Modelling was conducted using the Maxent function of the dismo R package (Hijmans et al., 2016). The idea of Maxent is to estimate target distributions by finding the distributions of maximum entropy using species occurrences and environmental variables (Phillips et al., 2006). Entire dataset was used for model building, without splitting. Maxent default settings were maintained. True Skill Statistic (TSS) was used as an eval-

uation measure, as recommended in Allouche et al., 2006. TSS values range from - 1 to + 1, where + 1 indicates perfect model agreement, while values of zero or less indicate a performance no better than random (Allouche et al., 2006).

Maps of current and future potential distributions for the year 2070 (average 2061–2080) were created. By applying the threshold maximizing the sum of sensitivity and specificity (Liu et al., 2013), maps were then transformed to binary format (showing suitable/unsuitable areas for species). Based on these maps, the potential area of occupancy (pAOO) for selected strictly protected species was calculated both for the present time and the future. By subtracting pAOO present from pAOO future, the potential range change for analysed hoverflies caused by global warming was assessed. Map visualization was conducted using DIVA-GIS version 7.5 software (Hijmans et al., 2012).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 10 species were included in the analysis. TSS values ranged from 0.53–0.98 (Table 1), which indicated generally a good fit of the models. Three out of 10 analyzed species were predicted to reduce their range in the future, while for 7 species models anticipated range expansion. Species showing the highest absolute loss of range for 2070 was *Neocnemodon larusi* (Vujić, 1999), while the highest relative loss was predicted for *Trichopsomyia flavitarsis* (Meigen, 1822), which will lose around 73% of its current range, according to the models. As for the gainers, *Cheilosia griseifacies* Vujić, 1994 was predicted to have the greatest absolute increase in range, while *Cheilosia melanura rubra* Vujić, 1996 was the species with the highest relative gain (Table 1).

Table 1. TSS values and pAOO values for the present time and 2070, absolute and relative change in pAOO between the present and projected future scenario for 10 strictly protected species of hoverflies in Serbia.

Species	TSS	pAOO present	pAOO 2070	absolute change	relative change
<i>Cheilosia griseifacies</i> Vujić, 1994	0.84	8,234.33	20,596.86	12,362.53	150.13
<i>Cheilosia insignis</i> Loew, 1857	0.69	26,101.42	8,981.19	-17,120.23	-65.59
<i>Cheilosia melanura rubra</i> Vujić, 1996	0.98	1,808.74	9,751.65	7,942.91	439.14
<i>Cheilosia schnabli</i> Becker, 1894	0.72	1,372.52	2,976.09	1,603.57	116.83
<i>Merodon desaturinus</i> Vujić, Simić, & Radenković, 1995	0.88	3,510.38	12,259.69	8,749.31	249.24
<i>Orthonevra montana</i> Vujić, 1999	0.93	5,703.60	5,832.95	129.34	2.27
<i>Sericomyia superbiens</i> (Muller), 1776	0.88	10,669.91	13,570.98	2,901.07	27.19
<i>Sphagina sublatifrons</i> Vujić, 1990	0.93	5,707.84	6,274.23	566.40	9.92
<i>Trichopsomyia flavitarsis</i> (Meigen), 1822	0.75	21,960.13	5,893.43	-16,066.70	-73.16
<i>Neocnemodon larusi</i> (Vujić), 1999	0.53	42,135.04	19,224.14	-22,910.90	-54.37

In general, more species were predicted to gain range across time, but differences between individual species are present, indicating the significance of biology and ecology for the response of the species to the changing climate. Several studies have already addressed the effects of climate change on hoverfly distribution across the Balkan Peninsula. Radenković et al. (2017) analysed genus *Cheilosia*, Kaloveloni et al. (2015) focused their research on the genus *Merodon*, while Miličić et al. (2018) forecasted the effects of climate change on 44 hoverfly species from southeastern Europe with restricted range. All these studies indicated the significance of altitude and habitat type for the species distribution. This premise is shown in this study as well.

Figure 1. Projected potential species richness of strictly protected species of hoverflies for the present time. Each cell represents the total number of species in defined grid cells.

Figure 2. Projected potential species richness of strictly protected species of hoverflies for 2070. Each cell represents the total number of species in defined grid cells.

Figure 3. Differences in species richness of hoverflies between 2070 and the present. Each cell represents the total number of species in defined grid cells.

Figure 1 shows current cumulative species richness, while the cumulative species richness for 2070 is presented in Figure 2. In both cases, similar areas were predicted to be most species rich, and these areas are mostly mountain-

ous, such as mountains Golija, Kopaonik and Prokletije in western Serbia and mountains Stara Planina, Besna Kobila, Suva Planina and Dukat in southeastern part of the country. Several studies indicated that climate change caused altitudinal range shifts (Hickling et al., 2006; Moritz et al., 2008; Kaloveloni et al., 2015; Radenković et al., 2017; Coals et al., 2018), because species follow favourable conditions, which become available only on the highest mountain peaks, as the temperature increases.

In Figure 3, changes in species richness between the present and 2070 are depicted. Mountains in southeastern Serbia are predicted to gain species over the time, as well as a patch in northwestern part of the Province of Vojvodina. Fruška Gora mountain and several mountains in central Serbia with lower altitudes are predicted to lose a part of their species.

Beside climate change, there are several other factors that may influence the future distribution of strictly protected syrphid species in Serbia. Land use and degradation of habitats represent some of the major threats for species survival in general (Novecek and Cleveland, 2001; Foley et al., 2005; Newbald et al., 2015), and this is the case with hoverflies as well. Considering that high mountain habitats are very often amongst the most threatened ones (Diaz et al., 2003), question arises whether these areas will have the capacity to support future hoverfly assemblages.

Additional argument that should be taken into consideration is the connection of syrphids with flowering plants. Hoverflies use flowering plants as a source of food. For some species (e.g. *Cheilosia* and *Merodon* species), the dependence on plants is even stronger, considering that larvae of these species develop in plant tissue (Speight, 2017). Climate change undoubtedly will affect plant species, and consequently the plant-insect networks as well.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it is predicted that climate change will have different effects on specific species of hoverflies designated as strictly protected in Serbia. Part of the species will experience range loss, while for others range expansions are predicted. High mountain areas are predicted to have the highest species richness over the time. The results of this study can contribute to planning future steps for the conservation of strictly protected hoverfly species.

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СТРОГО ЗАШТИЋЕНЕ ВРСТЕ ОСОЛИКИХ МУВА
(Diptera: Syrphidae) У ОГЛЕДАЛУ КЛИМАТСКИХ ПРОМЕНА

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РЕЗИМЕ: Због спектра могућих последица, услед климатских промена које се дешавају, бројне студије се баве испитивањем ефеката глобалног загревања на дистрибуцију врста. У оквиру ове студије, испитали смо утицај промене климе на дистрибуцију одабраних строго заштићених врста осоликих мува у Србији, користећи моделе потенцијалне дистрибуције. У анализу је било укључено 10 врста. За три врсте је предвиђено да током времена изгубе део свог ареала, док је за седам врста предвиђено проширење ареала. И у садашњости и у будућности, региони с највећим богатством врста су планински, као што су Голија, Копаоник и Проклетије у западној Србији, и Стара планина, Бесна кобила, Сува планина и планина Дукат у југоисточном делу земље. Ипак, поред климатских промена постоји више фактора који могу утицати на дистрибуцију строго заштићених врста у Србији: интензивно коришћење земљишта и деградација станишта. Додатно, глобално загревање утиче и на биљке цветнице, од којих су сирфиде зависне, што може представљати још једну препреку будућем ширењу њиховог ареала. Ови резултати могу допринети планирању будућих корака за конзервацију строго заштићених врста осоликих мува.

КЉУЧНЕ РЕЧИ: глобално загревање, инсекти, моделовање потенцијалне дистрибуције врста, строго заштићене врсте